

Silver in Ayurvedic Pharmaceuticals—A Spectrophotometric Study using Sodium Pentamethylene Dithiocarbamate

V. V. RAMANA and K. SARASWATHI*

Department of Chemistry, S. V. University, Tirupati-517 502

Manuscript received 26 August 1992, revised 3 December 1992, accepted 7 January 1993

In continuation of our earlier work on the spectrophotometric determination of metal ions¹ through complexation with sodium pentamethylene dithiocarbamate (Pipdte) and extraction in chloroform, we report here a general method of determination of silver(I) including the effect of foreign ions and its application in the estimation of silver in Ayurvedic medicines.

Results and Discussion

Neither the reagent nor the metal ion have any absorbance at 320 nm. The complex was stable for more than 4 h and complete extraction could be achieved in a single extraction with 2 min of shaking in the presence of magnesium sulphate. Maximum absorbance was observed in the pH range 5–8 (NaAc/HAc). The influence of the

reagent concentration for complete complex formation and influence of the salting-out agent for complete extraction in a single step have been examined. It is noticed that $5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Ag^{I} , 1.6 ml of $1.15 \times 10^{-4} M$ solution of (Pipdte) and 1 ml of $0.2 M$ MgSO_4 as salting-out agent are sufficient for quantitative extraction within 1–2 min of shaking. Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 1–5 μg of Ag^{I} in 10 ml of chloroform. The molar absorptivity of the complex is $4.25 \times 10^4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the Sandell's sensitivity (absorbance=0.001) is $0.00252 \mu\text{g cm}^2$. The composition of the complex determined by Job's method of continuous variation, mole-ratio method, Asmus method and curve-fitting method, was found to be 1:1 (metal: ligand). The instability constant of the complex calculated by Edmond's and Birnbaums methods, is 0.3791×10^{-6} at room temperature, which is in good agreement with the value (0.3682×10^{-6}) calculated by Asmus method.

Effect of foreign ions: Cations like Sn^{II} , V^{V} , Bi^{III} , Se^{IV} , U^{VI} , Al^{III} , Fe^{II} , Hg^{II} do not interfere even when present upto 100-folds and Fe^{III} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cr^{VI} , Ce^{IV} , Te^{IV} , Pd^{II} can be tolerated upto 60-folds with an error of $\pm 1\%$ in the absorbance value. Traces of Cu^{II} ($5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and Pb^{II} ($2 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) do not interfere. The interference due to Ni^{II} can be masked with iodate and fluoride whereas Co^{II} with citrate, tartrate and fluoride. Among the various anions studied thiocyanate is found to interfere.

Estimation of Ag in Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals: The procedure developed was applied for the estimation of silver in Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals. The samples were digested and brought into solution using the standard method². The amount of silver(i) present in the samples was determined by referring its absorbance values to the calibration curve drawn with standard solutions of Ag and the values were in good agreement with those obtained by standard silver chloride method² (Table 1).

The method is advantageous since it is free from the interference of the commonly interfering ions with its lowest detectable limit 0.1 ppm, and thus appears to be selective, specific and simple for the determination of silver in trace quantities.

Experimental

The ligand, Na(Pipdte) was prepared and recrystallised from benzene¹. A stock solution of the reagent was prepared in double-distilled water, stored in dark and its $1.15 \times 10^{-4} M$ solution was used. Ag^{I} solution was prepared by dissolving

TABLE 1—ESTIMATION OF SILVER WITH (Pipdte) IN AYURVEDIC PHARMACEUTICALS

Sl. no.	Name of Sample*	Amount of Ag^{I} found (mg g^{-1})		Relative error %
		Pipdte method	AgCl method	
1.	Rajitha Bhasmanu ^a	930.0	926.6	0.18
		936.0	936.0	
		932.0	930.8	
2.	Raupya (Chandi) Bhasma ^b	953.0	951.0	0.26
		964.0	960.0	
		955.0	953.0	
3.	Rajitha Chandrodayam ^a	560.0	559.8	0.16
		570.0	565.6	
		563.0	562.7	
4.	Chandravathi rasam ^a	500.0	499.4	0.41
		510.0	500.0	
		503.0	501.1	

*Purchased from: ^aVenkateswara Ayurved Nilayamu, Chintaluru; ^bShree Baidyanath Ayurvedic Bhavan Ltd., Calcutta.

AgNO_3 (AnalaR) in water containing a little nitric acid. Standard solution of diverse ions were prepared from their sulphates, or from sodium, potassium or ammonium salts. Buffer solutions of pH 2 to 7 and 7 to 11, were prepared by mixing suitable proportions of the solutions, each $0.2 M$ of CH_3COONa and CH_3COOH , and NH_4Cl and NH_4OH respectively. Magnesium sulphate (AnalaR) was used as a salting-out agent. Chloroform was distilled before use. All other chemicals were of A. R. grade unless otherwise mentioned. Absorbance measurements were made using a Shimadzu PR-1 spectrophotometer and pH adjustments on an Elico LI-10 pH meter.

Procedure: An aliquot (1 ml) of silver(I) solution ($5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), acetate buffer (pH ~ 6.0; 1.0 ml), salting-out agent ($0.1 M$ MgSO_4 ; 1.0 ml), the reagent (Pipdte) solution (1.6 ml) and distilled water were mixed to keep the volume 10 ml. The mixture was then shaken with chloroform (10 ml). After equilibration the water-insoluble yellow complex in chloroform was separated and the absorbance was measured at 320 nm against reagent blank.

References

- K. SARASWATHI, K. SANTHA and K. MEENA KUMARI, *Analyst*, 1990, 125, 465; V. V. RAMANA, M. D. RAMAIAH and K. SARASWATHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, 68, 178; K. SARASWATHI, V. V. RAMANA, K. SANTHA and M. D. RAMAIAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, 68, 116; K. SARASWATHI, K. SANTHA and K. JYOTHIRMAYI, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 1988, 4, 683.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis Including Elementary Instrumental Analysis", 3rd. ed., Longmans, London, 1961, pp. 266, 486.